

**ANALYSING THE EFFECT OF FINANCIAL KNOWLEDGE ON THE
FINANCIAL BEHAVIOUR OF UNIVERSITY STUDENTS IN INDIA**

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Abstract

This study aims to investigate the effect of financial knowledge on the financial behaviour of university students in India. Financial knowledge and financial behaviour are important dimensions of financial literacy and are part of our study. The survey research design method was used to fulfil the research objective. Online structured questionnaires were sent through various social media platforms. Non-probability convenience and snowball sampling techniques were used for data collection. The Average, percentage and linear regression analysis were applied for the data analysis. The regression model shows that financial knowledge brings a moderate positive change in the financial behaviour of the students. Demographic variables like age, gender, family income and education have a significant impact on the financial knowledge, financial behaviour and overall score of students. Non-major students have scored higher than the economic and business major students. In India, there are not many studies focused on financial knowledge, financial behaviour and other dimensions of financial literacy of students, hence this study is among the few studies in this area of research. Educational institutes can introduce better financial literacy programmes and courses for the students by knowing their importance. Financial institutions and governments can have more understanding of young individuals for better financial products and services and economic policies. Non-probability sampling techniques and a slightly low number of participants may have biased results which can be questionable for generalisation in larger samples and due to the online questionnaire, students could have responded non-seriously.

Keywords : Financial knowledge, Financial behaviour, University students, Regression Analysis, OECD

Introduction

The wealth of any nation lies in its human capital. Productive, innovative and healthy people can be a great asset for the economic development process. As we have seen in a developed nation, their human resources are more productive and innovative, which brings rapid economic growth; as a result, income distribution, industrial growth, and poverty reductions become possible. On the other side, developing countries are struggling to use their potential resources for economic development. Economic growth is critical for people's overall well-being. Financial resources are a boon for an individual's needs and economic activities. An individual has to focus on their finances by savings for future needs, investments to grow the money in hand and planning expenditure to achieve financial well-being. An economy with a robust financial system which can observe the extra money of the people and give it to the required one in the form of advances offers better economic output and a win-win situation for both sides of

individuals and industries. An efficient and vibrant financial system connects the different stakeholders of the economy, which facilitates the money supply and allows people to manage their finances judiciously by using different financial products and services. (Lusardi, 2015)

Financial knowledge and financial behaviour are significant dimensions of financial literacy, which are proposed by (Hung et al., 2009) and also used in other studies (R. Clark et al., 2017; Khan et al., 2017; Xiao et al., 2014). Financial Knowledge is about having the idea of financial concepts which are necessary to take financial decisions on a daily basis. Savings, investment and transactions-related information play a vital role in every individual to take optimal and judicious decisions for their financial well-being. (Md. Sapir @ Md. Shafik and Wan Ahmad, 2020; Dewi et al., 2020). It is one of the most important dimensions of financial literacy that explains the understanding of the financial concepts and theories; of the individuals, and it reflects the financial behaviour that finally leads to financial well-being. Individuals with higher financial knowledge and literacy are more likely to have higher wealth accumulation, better financial positions and less financial stress in their life (Lusardi & Mitchell, 2014; She et al., 2022; Xiao et al., 2014; Xiao & Porto, 2017).

Financial knowledge drives the saving habit of individuals, which helps in the nation's economic activities. and it enhances the domestic capital flow and reduces the risk of volatility of foreign direct investment. Promoting savings through financial education among the young from early life would increase investment and national savings. Aggregate savings increase domestic investments, achieve high economic growth, increase national income, and support the governments to work on poverty reduction by collecting more taxes (Ribaj & Mexhuani, 2021).

Financial behaviour is a reflective outcome of financial knowledge of how an individual takes a financial decision and spends his money on different things. Choosing long-term and short-term financial products and services based on his needs shows planned financial behaviour. An individual's daily financial activities require a positive financial orientation, like keeping an eye on his expenses, having a contingency fund, and regularly saving for short- and long-term needs (Dewi et al., 2020; Saurabh & Nandan, 2018). Negative financial behaviour of an individual when they make careless financial decisions, lives without financial goals in mind and depend on only employers and government pension funds.

Over the years, the focus of governments and employers has been reducing on the social benefits schemes for individuals and employees worldwide, leading to needing for individuals to take charge of their financial protection for life (Agarwalla et al., 2013; Annamaria Lusardi & Noemi Oggero, 2017). The previous research findings revealed that the level of financial literacy among adults could be better. This raises a serious challenge in front of the governments to bring more effective financial literacy programmes and strategies to improve the financial knowledge of young people. In response to improving individuals' financial knowledge, the Australian Securities and Investment Commission implemented National Financial Literacy Strategy in 2011, while New Zealand introduced National Strategy for Financial Literacy in 2008 was developed by Enterprise New Zealand Trust. The Financial Services Authority of the UK is also working to improve the financial literacy of the youth. In India, the Reserve Bank of India introduced the financial literacy programme in July 2012 to enhance the financial knowledge of the Indian youth and the general public (Agarwalla et al., 2013).

The purpose of this study is to examine the financial knowledge and financial behaviour levels of university students in India. Both are essential variables of financial literacy and are used to study in the Indian context. This study aims to check the financial knowledge and financial behaviour of young university-going adults and determine the relationship between these two variables. This is among only

a few studies in India to analyse and highlight the importance of financial knowledge among the young generation and its role in the nation's financial well-being and economic growth. Many studies have been done in different parts of the world to check students' financial literacy, especially high school students, and a few of them have been on college students as well. Studies on investors (Agarwal et al., 2015) and working professionals (Agarwalla et al., 2013) have been done in India also. This study is focused on university-going young adults. An attempt to fill the gap in the literature and explore patterns of financial knowledge and financial behaviour of young students in the Indian context. Objectives of the study: first to find out the level of financial knowledge and financial behaviour among university students. Second to understand how demographic variables affect the financial knowledge and financial behavior scores of students.

Literature Review

More often, financial literacy and financial knowledge are used interchangeably, but (Huston, 2010), in his study, distinguished financial knowledge and financial literacy and described financial literacy as having the knowledge of financial concepts and the same time, having the ability and confidence to apply this knowledge for better financial decisions making. It includes both financial knowledge and human capital. Financial Knowledge is the understanding of financial concepts which are necessary for individuals to take financial decisions on a daily basis. It includes savings, investment, and transactions related knowledge that play a key role in every individual's life to take the optimal and judicious decision for their own financial well-being (Atkinson & Messy, 2013; Bajaj & Kaur, 2022; Saurabh & Nandan, 2018). University students are in their development stage of financial knowledge and begin to learn financial concepts and manage them. It is crucial for them to get the proper financial education and resources to improve their financial knowledge and ability to use them; therefore, they can make informed financial decisions and achieve financial well-being. Some of the studies describe the two forms of financial knowledge: first, is perceived financial knowledge, which includes the subjective knowledge, abilities and confidence for making financial decisions and the second is actual financial knowledge which is objective knowledge of the individuals related to savings, investment, transactions and credit (Henager & Mauldin, 2015; Hwang & Park, 2022; Nguyen et al., 2017; Sam et al., 2022; Saurabh & Nandan, 2018). Individuals are required to have both types of financial knowledge in order to make informed financial decisions in their life. Actual financial knowledge of the individuals reflects on their saving behaviour and portfolio selection which helps in wealth accumulation and financial well-being (Hwang & Park, 2022; Lusardi & Tufano, 2015). Most studies have used simple questions related to inflations, interest rate calculation, time value of money concept, diversification, bonds and stocks, compounding interest and bank account types to check the basic financial knowledge of the individuals (Dewi et al., 2020; Nguyen et al., 2017). OECD is one of the prominent organisations in the field of finance and economics which has created measurement tools and methodology for financial literacy research around the world (NCFE-FLIS, 2019).

Individuals' financial knowledge changes their financial behaviour, and they exhibit sensible behaviour while making saving and investment-related decisions. More knowledgeable individuals tend to behave more responsibly compared to lower levels individuals. (Saurabh & Nandan, 2018). Financial Literacy changes the financial behaviour of individuals (Agarwalla et al., 2013; Henager & Mauldin, 2015; Lusardi & Mitchell, 2014; Lusardi & Tufano, 2015; Nguyen et al., 2017). Some of them say about it otherwise (Subarna Bir, 2016). Financial knowledge through proper financial education from the early stages becomes critically important to bring positive financial behaviour among the student. The need for financial literacy increases among the young generations because governments and employers continuously reduce their responsibility to social welfare schemes and financial security for retirement. During university, it is the best time for young students to learn the importance of financial planning,

retirement savings, and other social welfare financial products and to find out better financial products and services for their financial well-being. Low financial literacy cost higher transaction fees, more borrowing cost (de Bassa Scheresberg, 2013; Lusardi & Tufano, 2015), and lower savings (Stango & Zinman, 2009). And lack of retirement financial planning.

Previous studies in countries like the United States, United Kingdom, Europe, Australia, and Japan reveal low levels of financial literacy among most respondents (Hassan Al-Tamimi & Anood Bin Kalli, 2009). This is true all across the nations, regardless of their economic development. Low level of financial literacy among young adults is a major challenge around the globe (Agarwalla et al., 2013; Allgood & Walstad, 2013; Lusardi & Mitchell, 2014; van Rooij et al., 2011), 69% of adults have a bank account worldwide (Demirguc-Kunt et al., 2018; World Bank, 2018) and remaining 31% adults who do not have the bank account belongs to developing countries like Bangladesh, China, India, Indonesia, Mexico, Nigeria, and Pakistan (Demirguc-Kunt et al., 2018). Indonesia achieved 69% financial inclusion (Dewi et al., 2020). This has become important for every nation to address it. Studies show that higher financial literacy leads to better financial choices among individuals and, less affected by financial fraud, fewer financial problems compared to others. According to Mastercard's 2015 Financial Literacy Index, in developing countries index score has declined, as contrary to developed countries. (Klapper et al., 2015) mentioned that people's financial knowledge differs in developed and developing countries adults. A dire need arises to enhance the financial literacy of people of all ages. Financial and maths education can be more effective for developing financial literacy among students, and cultural perceptions also play a key role in early life development (Al-Bahrani et al., 2020). Improving financial literacy would result in greater financial inclusion and financial stability among young generations. It is also very pertinent for them to have sound financial knowledge and decision-making skills to achieve greater financial success. Financial literacy was found to be a major contributor to financial satisfaction, as mentioned in his study (Ali et al., 2015). Higher financial literacy indicates higher financial satisfaction in individuals (Xiao et al., 2014), and a low level of financial literacy could lead to credit mismanagement, bankruptcy and over-credit in an individual's life. Six key dimensions of financial well-being identified by (Mugenda & Hira, 1998) are the amount of savings, money owed, current financial situation, ability to meet long-term goals, preparedness to meet emergencies and financial management skills. Studies mentioned that there is a gender gap in terms of financial literacy scores; men typically show higher levels of financial literacy than women (Atkinson & Messy, 2013). The education level of individuals also impacts the financial literacy score (Atkinson & Messy, 2012; Lusardi & Mitchell, 2011) as its increases with financial literacy increases. This also differs based on the type of investors; aggressive investors are more likely to answer correctly than conservative investors, and respondents having more goals, investments and liabilities; can answer more financial literacy questions; however, when they have too many goals, investment and liabilities; their financial literacy found decreasing. Individuals who choose aggressive growth strategies tend to have more insurance plans than their other counterparts (Agarwal et al., 2015).

Hypothesis

H₁. There is no significant effect of financial knowledge on the financial behaviour of university students.

Research Methodology

Conducting this study, a survey research design was used in this research paper; it is considered to be an appropriate design to collect numerical data from a larger population. Five-point Likert scale-based structured questionnaires were sent to the central university students through online platforms like WhatsApp and LinkedIn. Convenience and snowball non - probability sampling methods were used to collect the responses from the students. Participants were chosen based on their interests to participate

and were pre-informed about their shared data that will be only used for academic purposes. This method is very useful when the list of the total respondents is not available for randomisation. The respondents of this study are students of undergraduate degrees, postgraduate degrees, diploma courses and doctorate degree programmes at central universities in India.

The questionnaire was sent to the students whose contact details were available and were also asked to forward or arrange the contact of other students. This was sent to approximately 360 university-going students, and they are mostly from central universities in India. Out of these, 120 responses were received, and all were used for analysis. Two major variables of financial literacy– financial knowledge and financial behaviours, which have 22 questions; are the dimensions of this study. To measure the financial knowledge construct, 13 questions were adopted from (Bajaj & Kaur, 2022; NCFE-FLIS, 2019) studies and for the financial behaviour, 9 questions were adopted from (NCFE-FLIS, 2019; Potrich & Vieira, 2018). Average, percentage and simple linear regression were used for the data analysis.

Data Analysis and Results

Participation of the respondents for this study, where males are 56.67% (n=68), 42.50% (n=51) females and 1 respondent chosen prefer not to say option. Bifurcation of the students based on their residence state, 3.33% (n=4) students from Bihar, 20.83% (n=25) from Chhattisgarh, 3.33% (n=4) from Delhi, 3.33% (n=4) from Himachal Pradesh, 0.83% (n=1) from Jammu and Kashmir, 0.83% (n=1) from Jharkhand, 3.33% (n=4) from Kerala, 38.33% (n=46) from Madhya Pradesh, 0.83% (n=1) from Tamil Nadu, 23.33% (n=28) from Uttar Pradesh, and 1.67% (n=2) from West Bengal. Respondent's age groups are 25% (n=30) belonging to 15-20 years, 29.17% (n=35) 21-25 years, 27.50% (n=33) 26-30 years, 10.83% (n=13) 31-35 years and 7.50% (n=9) belongs to more than 35 years. Respondents group based on family income are 59.17% (n=71) belonging to up to 5 lakhs, 15.83% (n=19) from 6-10 lakhs, 13.33% (n=16) from 11-15 lakhs, 5% (n=6) from 16-20 lakhs, 6.67% (n=8) from more than 20 lakhs. Respondents in terms of education level are 1.67% (n=2) belong to Diploma courses, 25% (n=30) from Undergraduate, 30.83% (n=37) from Postgraduate and 42.50% (n=51) are from Doctorate level.

Scoring Method of Financial Knowledge, Financial Behaviour and Total Score

The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) has created one standardised tool kit for financial literacy-related research around the world. With an objective to produce comparable results from different respondents from different countries. The scoring method as prescribed in this document is like 0 scores assigned for the negative answer and 1 score for the positive response. All the positive scores have been added and then converted in percentage with respect to the total maximum score (NCFE-FLIS, 2019). This study emulated similar methods for the calculation of financial knowledge and financial behaviour scores of the students. The financial knowledge construct has 13 questions and each question had a maximum 5 score. Based on the options on Likert based questions, numbers were assigned for the calculation purpose. Strongly agree has a (5) point score, similarly agree (4), neither agree nor disagree (3), disagree (2) and strongly disagree has a (1) score point. And reverse scoring for negative questions. Maximum 65 and minimum 13 scores in financial knowledge respondents were able to achieve and the total number was calculated by adding all the scores based on the selected option on each question and that score was converted into percentages through the total achieved score divided by the maximum score of the construct. The financial behaviour construct has 9 questions and students can score a maximum of 45 and a minimum of 9 as each question carry the highest 5 points and a minimum of 1 point based on a Likert scale from highest strongly agree to lowest strongly disagree. The total score is calculated by adding the scores of financial knowledge and financial behaviour of the students.

i.) Financial Knowledge, Financial Behaviour and Total Score with Age Group (Author's calculation)

As the results of this survey show that as individuals get older their financial knowledge and financial behaviour scores improve over the years. Previous studies (Bajaj & Kaur, 2022; Karakurum-Ozdemir et al., 2019) have also revealed similar results and at the same time, there are few studies (Hassan Al-Tamimi & Anood Bin Kalli, 2009) age of the individuals do not impact the overall score.

Age Group	Respondents in %	FK Score in %	FB Score in %	Total Score	Total Score in %
15-20	25.00%	66.77%	73.46%	76.46	69.51%
21-25	29.17%	73.14%	76.68%	82.05	74.59%
26-30	27.50%	73.09%	81.26%	84.08	76.44%
31-35	10.83%	69.95%	81.17%	82.30	74.82%
35+	7.50%	77.77%	79.00%	86.11	78.28%

ii.) Financial Knowledge, Financial Behaviour and Total Score with Gender

Male respondents scored more than female participants which states that gender has an impact on overall score. Studies (Bajaj & Kaur, 2022; Hassan Al-Tamimi & Anood Bin Kalli, 2009; Karakurum-Ozdemir et al., 2019) are in line with this study.

Gender	Respondents in %	FK Score in %	FB Score in %	Total Score	Total Score in %
Male	56.67%	72.26%	79.27%	82.64	75.13%
Female	42.50%	70.91%	75.47%	80.05	72.77%

iii.) Financial Knowledge, Financial Behaviour and Total Score with Income Level

Based on the income level of participants' families, this study highlights the financial knowledge and financial behaviour score of the different income groups of students. The family income of the participants has also an impact on their financial knowledge and financial behaviour score. These studies (Agarwalla et al., 2013; Bajaj & Kaur, 2022; Hassan Al-Tamimi & Anood Bin Kalli, 2009; Karakurum-Ozdemir et al., 2019) highlight a similar outcome. Another study conducted by (Agarwal et al., 2015) presented it otherwise.

Income Level	Respondents in %	FK Score in %	FB Score in %	Total Score	Total Score in %
Up to 5 Lakhs	59.17%	70.74%	78.29%	81.21	73.83%
6-10 Lakhs	15.83%	74.65%	80.58%	84.78	77.07%
11-15 Lakhs	13.33%	72.88%	77.91%	82.43	74.94%
16-20 Lakhs	5.00%	73.32%	77.78%	82.66	75.15%
More than 20 Lakhs	6.67%	67.88%	66.67%	74.12	67.38%

iv.) Financial Knowledge, Financial Behaviour and Total Score with Education Level

The education level of the students has also impacted their financial knowledge, financial behaviour and overall score. An outcome of this study says that the education level of the students has a positive

impact on the overall score of financial literacy dimensions. Other studies (Agarwal et al., 2015; Atkinson & Messy, 2012; Bajaj & Kaur, 2022; Bumcrot et al., 2011; de Bassa Scheresberg, 2013; Lusardi & Mitchell, 2011) also gave the same results.

Education Level	Respondents in %	FK Score in %	FB Score in %	Total Score	Total Score in %
DIP	1.67%	61.54%	71.11%	72.00	65.45%
UG	25.00%	68.20%	76.36%	78.69	71.54%
PG	30.83%	71.38%	75.56%	80.40	73.09%
PhD	42.50%	74.11%	80.56%	84.42	76.75%

v.) **Financial Knowledge, Financial Behaviour and Total Score with Discipline**

Students who have studied Economics or business major subjects account for 78.33% of total respondents have achieved 71.57% in financial knowledge, 77.49% in financial behaviour and 73.99% in combined scores. Non-economics or business major students account for 21.67% of total respondents have scored 71.67% in financial knowledge, 78.96% in financial behaviour and 74.64% in combined score. Non-major students have achieved more than the major students although they haven't studied. The possible reason could be, in the major student's category, the number of UG and PG respondents is more; as compared to non-major and they have also shown low scores in both dimensions that ultimately impacted the overall category score.

Discipline	Respondents in %	FK Score in %	FB Score in %	Total Score	Total Score in %
Economics and Business Major	78.33%	71.57%	77.49%	81.39	73.99%
Non-Major	21.67%	71.65%	78.96%	82.10	74.64%

vi.) **Regression Analysis** (Source: Author's calculation)

In the model of estimation R value 0.502 indicate that the correlation between financial knowledge and financial behaviour is moderate which means as the financial knowledge of students increases it also leads to an increase in financial behaviour but this is not strongly correlated. The R^2 value of the regression analysis is 0.252 which highlights that only 25% of changes in dependent variable financial behaviour happen due to independent variable financial knowledge and the remaining changes depend on the factors.

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
0.502	0.252	0.246	4.491

Conclusion

This research paper studied two of its major components which are financial knowledge and financial behaviour with an objective to find out the relationship between these two dimensions among university-going students. This study tested the difference in the mean score of the students who studied economics and finance major and non-major in their student life. And also checked the effect of demographic variables like age, gender, income, education and discipline on the financial knowledge and financial behaviour score of the students. Linear regression analysis results are strong ($R^2 = 0.252$) which explains the 25.20 percent variable in the financial behaviour happens from the financial knowledge of the

students. As a result, the findings related to the effect of financial knowledge on financial behaviour in this study are in line with older studies (Agarwalla et al., 2013). Learning financial skills at a very young age and reflecting on the behaviour is crucial for young adults as they have long years to live and this brings financial stability by covering the needs for future requirements.

The hypothesis says that there is no significant effect of financial knowledge on the financial behaviour of university students is rejected since our findings show the significant effect of financial knowledge on the financial behaviour of respondents. The third and last hypothesis was there are no significant differences in the mean score of the students based on the demographic profile (Age, Gender, Income, and Education) of the students was also rejected. The results tell that age, gender, income and education have a significant impact on the combined score of financial knowledge and financial behaviour.

Since the findings of this study point out that financial knowledge greatly enhances the financial behaviour of individuals and during this stage of life they learn things quickly then it becomes very important for the students to get accomplished in financial knowledge and related skills.

This study has implications for several stakeholders. Young students and individuals can make themselves aware of the importance of financial knowledge and its application to bring it into their behaviour. Educational institutions can take more initiatives to create financial awareness by starting different training programmes and courses for students and individuals. Similarly, this can also be replicated by financial institutions and the government. Government can bring different policies where ample opportunities would be available for our younger generation to learn how to deal with financial stuff in their life. Learning these things will give them confidence and skills to handle their finances judiciously and achieve financial satisfaction and well-being.

While conducting this study all the necessary precautions have been taken but still, this study also has some limitations; one could be the data collection method which was convenient and snowballed. As it does not follow randomised techniques that may be affected the results. The second limitation of this could be the number of sample sizes.

Future studies can take up these limitations of this study and try to find the results with a large number of participants and randomised data for better estimations of financial literacy scores. Other dimensions of financial literacy can also be included while working in this field of study.

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